

Design and Working of Pedal Operated Flour Mill

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ABSTRACT

Due to industrial development, use of natural fuel is increasing continuously that's why there is need of alternating source of senergy. Eg Human energy.

To reduce use of natural fuel we can use bicycle technology to run a machine using human power.

Dynapods (Greek word) for power and foot. Dynapods can be run by one or two person.

We are transmitting rotary motion from paddle to wheel of mill. Human input is low as compare to hand operated machine

Keywords: industrial deploement, energy, human energy, bicycle technology, dynapods, rotary motio, pedal operated machine, natural fuel etc

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Introduction

Keeping these limitations of human capabilities in mind the proposed machine consists of three sub systems:

1. The energy unit,
2. Transmission mechanism
3. The process unit.

Paddling power= 4X handling power

If it will be run by ¼ horse power then a person can work for 10 minutes.

If it will be run by 1/8 horse power then a person can work for 60 minutes.

94Watt(.12HP) can be maintained for 60 minutes or more.

DESIGN

Pedal Power

$$T = 7 \times 9.81 \times 170 = 11673.9 \text{ Nm}$$

$$= 11.6739 \text{ Nm}$$

$$\text{Power} = (2 \times 3.14 \times 70 \times 11.6739) / 60$$

$$= 85.53 \text{ W}$$

$$N_a = 70 \text{ rpm}$$

$$T_a = 44$$

$$N_b = ?$$

$$T_b = 18$$

$$N_a / N_b = T_b / T_a = 18 / 44 = 0.409$$

$$N_b = 171.11 \text{ rpm}$$

Wheel Design Of Mill

$$\text{Diameter of cycle's wheel} = 50.8 \text{ cm}$$

$$\text{Diameter of mill's wheel} = 22 \text{ cm}$$

$$N_c = N_b = 171.11 \text{ rpm}$$

$$N_c / N_d = D_b / D_c = 50.8 / 22$$

$$N_d = 395.10 \text{ rpm}$$

DESIGN OF CHAIN

$$\text{Pitch of chain} = [2 \times 3.14 (R_a + R_b)] / (T_a + T_b)$$

$$= [2 \times 3.14 \times (100 + 45)] / (44 + 18)$$

$$= 14.68 \text{ mm}$$

Design of V belt

It depends on speed of driving and driven Power

Center Distance

Speed ratio

Service Condition

$$\text{Speed Ratio} = N_d / N_c = 395.1 / 171.11 = 2.309$$

According to this speed ratio

$$\text{Diameter Factor} = 1.13 \text{ (Design data book)}$$

$$\text{Equivalent dia} = 220 \times 1.13 = 248.6 \text{ mm}$$

Based on this we select belt cross section

$$V = 3.14 \times D_d \times N_d / 60 = 3.14 \times 220 \times 395.1 / 60$$

$$= 4.548 \text{ m/sec}$$

Power transmission capacity

$$N^* = v(1.47/v^{0.09} - 143.27/De - 2.34v^2/10^4)$$

$$= 3.1917KW$$

Based on these factor V belt of 'C' type.

Upper width=22mm

Thickness=14mm

T=torque

Na=rotational speed of larger spoked

Nb= rotational speed of smaller spoked

Nc= rotational speed of rare wheel

Nd= rotational speed of wheel of mill

Ta=teeth on larger spoked

Tb= teeth on smaller spoked

Working concept and Model

In conventional stone wheel mechanism the intermittent flow is required to get fine output. The same type of arrangements of flow is made in Pedal operated flour mill.

It consists of Hopper mechanism in which the grains are stored. It is having a flow control unit, which is connected by means of mechanical spring to the left hand brakes.

By breaking, the flow may control. The output of the stone wheel mechanism is collected between a hemispherical collector which is located below the stone wheel mechanism. The energy unit basically consists of conventional bicycle mechanism; the transmission mechanism consists of chain drive running over a pair of sprockets and belt drive running over pulley and stone wheels

The process unit is a pair of stone wheels mounted over one another where the wheat gets crushed into powered form to produce wheat flour. All these units are assembled on bicycle like structure (seat , saddle , handle etc).

Drive unit:

This is first stage of transmission. The transmission of power from human to processing unit is carried out in two stages namely chain drive and belt drive. The operators uses his feet & legs to rotate pedal around the crank axel.

- 1-Front Chain Sprocket, 2-Pedal ,3-Chain ,4-Rear chain sprocket 5-Bearings for belt drive shaft , 7-CrossV Belt, 8-Stonewheels

References

- [1] Prasad A. Hatwalne, Sushil T. Ambadkar, R.V.Paropate, Vivek R. Gandhewar, A. M. Wankhade "Design and development of Pedal operated flour mill." New York Science Journal, 2011;
- [2] P.B. Khope, J. P Modak "Development and Performance Evaluation of a Human Powered Flywheel Motor Operated Forge Cutter." international journal of scientific & technology research volume 2, issue 3, March 2013.
- [3] Design Data , Data book of Engineers, (ISBN 978-81-927355-0-4, Compiled by PSG College of Engineering and Published by Kalaikathir Achchagam, Coimbatore, India)
- [4] International Journal of Latest Engineering and Management Research (IJLEMR) ISSN: 2455-4847
- [5] H. J. Hopfen (1969): Farm Implements for Arid and Tropical Regions Published by Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Via delle Terme di Caracalla 00100 Rome, Italy. Published in AT Microfiche Reference Library, pp.150
- [6] David Gordon Wilson (1986): Understanding Pedal Power, A Technical Paper-51, Published in Volunteers in Technical Assistance, ISBN: 0-86619-268-9